

Integrating Digital Twin And Mixed Reality In Human-Robot Collaboration

Mohammad Shaaban *

Simone Macciò

Alessandro Carfi

Fulvio Mastrogiovanni

Abstract—This paper proposes a novel software architecture for generalized scenarios of human-robot collaboration, in which a Digital Twin mirrors, monitors, and guides the interaction in real time, while Mixed Reality is used as a medium to ensure intuitive communication between agents involved.

Index Terms—Digital Twin, Mixed Reality, Human-Robot Collaboration, Software Architecture.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of human-centered manufacturing and smart factories, the concept of Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) is becoming more and more significant, both from a research and industrial point of view. In HRC, humans and robots coexist in the same physical place sharing tasks [1], combining the advantages of human cognitive skills with machine efficiency and speed. To achieve a natural form of collaboration between such agents, however, there are still multiple research aspects to tackle, ranging from the safety of the human workers throughout the cooperation to an efficient and effective communication between the interacting parties. To address these issues, a new era of Digital Twins (DTs) started emerging, benefiting from the recent improvements in networks communication speed, computing power and connectivity. In a DT, the work environment and all the agents (robots and humans) involved in the collaboration are reflected in real-time into a simulation to perform data-driven operations which help monitor and guide the cooperation itself, while ensuring its degree of safety [2]. At the same time, to guarantee a more robust and unambiguous communication between agents, researchers explored the adoption of Mixed Reality (MR) in HRC [3], combining it with wearable Head-Mounted Displays (HMDs). Leveraging MR as a communication layer, it is in fact possible to build intuitive holographic interfaces, which let human operators understand and anticipate the robot's intentions and upcoming actions, potentially leading to a smoother and more natural collaboration process [4], with fewer down-times and consequent increased productivity.

As such, this paper's contribution consists in a novel and modular software architecture, which combines a DT, whose goal is to mirror the current state of the interaction and guide the robot's control logic, together with a MR communication layer, devised to help the human agent understand and

This paper is supported by the European Union Erasmus+ Programme via the Master programme European Master on Advanced Robotics Plus (EMARO+).

All authors are with the Department of Informatics Bioengineering, Robotics and System Engineering (DIBRIS), University of Genoa, Genoa, Italy

* mohammad.shaaban@edu.unige.it

Fig. 1: Picture of a HRC scenario during an handover interaction, taken from external and DT perspectives.

proactively react to the robot's intentions within a generalized context of HRC.

II. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The proposed software architecture is depicted in Fig. 3 and consists, overall, of three main components: on the one hand, the Robot Operating System (ROS) [5] framework has been used to implement all of the modules (*nodes*) dealing with the logic and control of the robot. On the other hand, the DT which reflects the HRC scenario in real-time has been implemented with Unreal Engine 4 (UE4). Finally, the holographic communication interface has been developed as a MR application in Unity and later deployed on the HMD device. In particular, communication between ROS and the other two components is achieved with the help of open-source adapters, respectively for the ROS-Unity communication¹ and for interfacing ROS with UE4².

¹https://github.com/Unity-Technologies/Unity-Robotics-Hub/tree/main/tutorials/ros_unity_integration

²http://wiki.ros.org/rosbridge_suite

